

CALIPER
Gender Equality in STEM Research

Linking Research & Innovation for
Gender Equality

D6.7: Role Models Report

WP6: Dissemination and Communication
Version: 1.0

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Executive Summary

The purpose of this report, which is Deliverable 6.7 of the CALIPER project, is to summarise the process of creating nine promotional videos, and to assess their subsequent impact. The videos are intended to go beyond traditional 'success stories'. Instead, they present women at different career stages, with diverse cultural and scientific backgrounds in STEM, and highlights the institutional and cultural barriers they faced and what motivated them.

Filmed in the appropriate local language and with subtitles in English, the videos are used internally at each RPO/RFOs to raise awareness, generate debate and complement actions on attracting/retaining supporting female researchers. The aim was also the promotion of the role models from industry in order to raise awareness and motivate girls to enrol in STEM University studies, but also to support them as undergraduates and during their research careers.

In addition, through the leveraging effect of two pan-European academies in CALIPER (Academia Europaea and the Young Academy of Europe), the videos are intended to have a multiplying EU-wide effect. The deliverable summarises the process of selecting the interviewees and of producing the videos. The report then describes in detail how the videos were promoted, the main channels used and what their impact has been. Having met and exceeded the agreed KPIs, we conclude that the CALIPER role model videos have been an effective tool in promoting gender equality in STEM fields. The videos will continue to be watched beyond the lifetime of the CALIPER project, contributing to CALIPER's legacy and longer-term impact.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose & Scope

The purpose of this deliverable is to report on the creation of promotional videos, one for each of the RPOs/RFOs in the CALIPER project. Being an important part of CALIPER's online communications strategy, the videos are designed to raise awareness, generate debate, and complement actions on attracting, retaining, and supporting female researchers in STEM fields. They are intended to showcase the experiences of women with diverse cultural and scientific backgrounds who have overcome institutional and cultural barriers to become researchers, professors, and deans in STEM. The goal is to have a multiplying EU-wide effect on promoting gender diversity in research and innovation.

The work was initially led by the Young Academy of Europe (YAE), but was taken over by a new beneficiary, Cardiff University (CU) partway through the project. CU collaborated with VIL, as well as the participating RPOs and RFOs, on each video, from initial planning through to end promotion.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The purpose of this report is to summarise the entire process for the videos, from concept and creation, to launch, marketing and impact measurement. Section 1 outlines the scope and structure of the deliverable and relation to Task 6.3. Section 2 covers the role model videos, with a clear summary of the process overview and the promotion and impact of the videos. Each video has its own section, with a detailed summary of dissemination activities with images of these activities.

Section 3 focuses on the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), with an overview of the deliverables and milestone outcomes. The report ends with the Conclusion in Section 4, and a review of whether the CALIPER role model videos have been an effective tool in promoting gender equality in STEM fields.

1.3 Relation to Task 6.3 External communication and multiplying effect

The role model videos produced as part of the CALIPER project serve multiple purposes within Task 6.3, which focuses on external communication and multiplying the impact of the project. They are intended for internal use at each RPO/RFO to raise awareness, generate discussion, and support efforts to attract, retain and support female researchers. These videos are designed to complement and enhance ongoing initiatives and activities focused on promoting gender equality in research and academia.

In addition to their internal use, the videos have a multiplying effect across the EU by leveraging the presence of two professional associations within the CALIPER consortium. One of these is Academia Europaea, which has a knowledge hub located at Cardiff University and whose staff contribute to the CALIPER project. Academia Europaea Cardiff is also a member of the SAPEA (Science for Policy by European Academies) consortium, which operates at the science-policy interface and can reach an audience of academics, academies and policymakers. The other association is the Young Academy of Europe, which is affiliated with Academia Europaea. Through their participation in the CALIPER project, these associations provide a network of excellent researchers and ERC grant holders who can share the videos and their insights with their colleagues and peers throughout the EU. This dissemination of information and best practices helps to amplify the impact of the CALIPER project and contributes to the overall goal of advancing gender equality in research and academia.

2 Role Model Videos

2.1 Process overview

Prior to starting the preparations for the entire series of role model interviews, it had been mutually agreed by YAE (initial Task 6.3 leader) and VIL (WP6 leader and project coordinator) to work on a pilot video. The rationale was to organise a pilot and ground-setting role model interview to act as a production test and better anticipate how the interviews would be planned and performed. It was filmed in-person by YAE, and the outcome was satisfactory. Having done so, the series of role model interviews has been kick-started and partners were all aware of the required efforts.

The initial video completed by YAE (UZG-FER) was filmed remotely due to COVID-19 lockdown restrictions. The second video with SRNSFG was filmed in person, as at this point there were less restrictions.

Once CU took over the remaining videos, we developed our own process for planning each video. The initial process for beginning each video involved meeting with the relevant RFO/RPO to discuss the video and intended usage, so that CU could best determine our approach during the early planning stage.

As the first four videos that CU actioned were planned when COVID-19 restrictions made in-person activities difficult, these were filmed remotely; they were for NTUA, UEFISCDI, UNILE and IRB. Later video recordings were able to take place in person; these were for YU, ULB and STU BA. The basic initial process of creating the videos remained the same across the partners board, but variations were made according to the preferences of the particular RFO/RPO. For example, ULB Belgium wanted a role model video they could show to a particular target group (young girls in primary school) and so ULB worked together to outline a video brief that specifically catered to this market, involving several role models across a range of career points.

The selection process for the role models remained the same for all videos. The RFO/RPO would identify a potential role model, with reasoning as to why they wished to interview this person and share their selection with CU. CU would complete background research on the role model to determine suitability, and contact VIL and SV with an outline of the proposal. If VIL and SV approved the role model, the interview planning began. Fortunately, we were never in the position to restart the selection process, as all role models were approved.

Figure 1. Flow chart process for role model selection

It was important to interview a diverse range of role models, covering a wide range of career stages, subjects, and backgrounds. We interviewed women in both academia and industry, ranging from very early career stage to women who were at a later phase in their professions and had achieved renown in their field.

From this point, most videos followed the same process of CU project-managing the videos, with input from the partner. Two of the partners (STU BA and YU) completed their own filming and editing independently, and the two first videos (SRNSFG and UZG-FER) were completed by the YAE. For all interviews CU was involved with, CU either drafted or had input on the interview questions and filming script. Each role model had extensive background research completed by CU, in order to tailor the questions to their particular background and areas of interest. An interview script was also completed and provided to the interviewee and role model ahead of filming to ensure they were comfortable on the day of filming and able to prepare their answers in advance. NTUA, UEFISCDI, UNILE and IRB were filmed remotely side by side in a podcast style, i.e., the interviewer and role model both speaking to camera, and then this footage was edited into an interview format, with the viewpoint switching between whoever was talking. This allowed for a better visual and informal interview style. CU also located external footage of the role models via other routes (for example, for the NTUA role model video CU was able to obtain footage of the interviewee in her lab, from a previous interview) and once approval had been sought, footage was added to the final version to give context and additional engaging visuals.

All videos were filmed in the local language to enable local dissemination, and to give partners the option of which language they wanted to share the video in, given the primary language of their institution and target audience. Subtitles were completed in both the language of the interview and in English, allowing for both local dissemination and wider sharing, and this is continued across the shorter social media promotional videos as well.

2.2 Promotion & Impact

The CALIPER [role models page](#) is the central point for video promotion, as every video launch begins with an initial post on the main website. It has been key that the interview videos are posted in one location (the [CALIPER YouTube](#) account) with activity driven back to this video posting to accurately monitor views and KPIs. CALIPER also promotes each role model video via its regular [newsletter](#), sent to a recipient list of around 230 subscribers (screenshots under the relevant role model video). The project also heavily promotes videos via its social media channels (Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn) which have an accumulative reach of over 2300 people.

Role Models
Remarkable personalities, achievements and positive stories from female scientists across STEM fields

CALIPER Role Model Interviews

CALIPER PRO and RFO partners interview exceptional female researchers in their respective areas to create promotional videos thus raising awareness and generating debate about gender inequality issues in STEM fields.

Assoc. Professor Ing. Ivona Čerňáková
Faculty of Materials Science and Technology, Slovak University of Technology
"I would like to introduce science to people in such a way that it reveals the secrets that are part of our lives and the secrets of nature. If a girl likes STEM sciences, she should not be discouraged and guided by prejudices, but follow her feelings!"
WATCH THE INTERVIEW

ULB Spotlight: Women in STEM
Université Libre de Bruxelles
"Science is not male or female- it is a choice, and it is your choice. It is an infinite universe where we all can always learn more."
WATCH THE INTERVIEW

Prof. Dr. Özgen Özer
Ege University
"Many young people can go great miles when they are given the opportunity and path. I advise them to never lose their motivation!"
WATCH THE INTERVIEW

Dr Adriana Albini
University of Milano-Bicocca
"I want young women to not stop fighting."
WATCH THE INTERVIEW

Professor Ángela Nieto
Institute of Neurosciences in Alicante, Spain

Lecturer Dr Virginia Petre
Polytechnica University of Bucharest, Romania

Figure 2. CALIPER website

Cardiff University has prioritised the role model videos on its Cardiff Knowledge Hub Academia Europaea website, with a #rolemodel hashtag that directs website traffic to [all the interviews](#) in the series. Every interview is prominently promoted on the homepage of the website (example below) and a written transcription of the PDF editorial of the video is created in both the original language and English ([example](#)).

The Academia Europaea (Academy of Europe) has a thriving membership of more than 5,000 world-leading researchers, amongst them more than 80 Nobel laureates. At AE's Cardiff Hub, we promote research excellence for policy and progress.

Figure 3. CU's AE Knowledge Hub website

In addition to this, each video has an agreed upon communications plan (between the partner, CU and VIL) prior to launch, so campaigns are rolled out in a consistent manner. Individual promotions (such as newsletters) are listed under the relevant partner heading throughout this report. CU's AE Knowledge Hub's newsletter is sent to over 5000 members of Academia Europaea, a membership base of outstanding scholars across a wide spectrum of disciplines, and every video actioned by CU has been shared with this dedicated audience.

Videos filmed since CU's involvement have been edited into shortened versions of the interview; a two minute 'highlight reel' and two 30-second videos with particularly engaging quotes. These have been a critical part of the promotional campaign, as social media has featured heavily in the promotion of videos. Social media has allowed us to reach the broadest and most relevant audience, with AE Cardiff Hub's near 1k twitter following the ideal mix of academics, researchers, and industry, making it an ideal target audience for dissemination of the role model videos. AE Cardiff's role in the [SAPEA project](#) also gives us a wide network of policymakers that can be reached.

The YAE has also promoted the initial three videos they completed via their main channels; Twitter, their website and their monthly newsletter. Their website has a dedicated CALIPER [interview page](#) where the videos they have completed are promoted, as well as CALIPER information. They also have a dedicated [newsletter page](#) where previous communications can be browsed, and a newsletter subscriber base of 412 academic and industry recipients.

2.3 Pilot video

Responsible partner	YAE	Contributing partner(s)	VIL
Role model interviewee	Professor Moniek Tromp		
Background information	Professor Moniek Tromp is the Chair of Materials Chemistry at Groningen University and the Vice-Chair of the YAE by the time the interview was conducted. Currently, she is the head Chair of the YAE.		
Production process	This interview was organised as a pilot and ground-setting role model interview to establish the role model series, and act as a test to anticipate how the formal interviews may be actioned. It was filmed in-person by YAE.		
Dissemination of the interview	<p>To promote the video, an initial Tweet was sent out to YAE's Twitter followers with a short video quote from the video, as well as a launch tweet from CALIPER. CALIPER also included promotion for the video in their July 2021 newsletter. The video was further promoted on Twitter as part of YAE's 2021 International Women's Day socials, and YAE included a spotlight in their January 2023 newsletter of this and other role model interviews. As of April 2023, the video has received 255 views on YouTube.</p>		

Figure 4. YAE Tweet

Figure 5. CALIPER tweet

Inspiring stories from women in STEM fields research

Gender Equality in STEM Research (CALIPER) produces videos and interviews to raise awareness and generate debate about gender inequality issues in STEM fields. The interviewees are role models with achievements and positive stories that encourage other women, especially young girls, to become engaged with research and innovation. YAE's Chair and Professor of Materials Chemistry at Groningen University, Moniek Tromp, is one of the role models interviewed. For more information on the CALIPER series see [here](#).

Figure 6. YAE newsletter

Link to the
YouTube video

Link to video on YouTube

2.4 University of Zagreb, UZG-FER (Croatia)

Responsible partner	UZG-FER	Contributing partner(s)	VIL
Role model interviewee	Professor Ivana Podnar Žarko		
Background information	Professor Ivana Podnar Žarko is Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing, University of Zagreb and Technical Manager of the H2020 project symbloTe: Symbiosis of smart objects across IoT environments. She has also participated in a number of research projects (EU-funded and national) and was chosen for her cross-experience in both academia and industry, co-authoring more than 70 scientific journal and conference papers.		
Production process	The first role model video to be completed was actioned by YAE in April 2021, in collaboration with partner UZG-FER in Croatia.		
Dissemination of the interview	The launch promotions were largely Twitter based, with CALIPER tweeting about the video and Professor Podnar Žarko's lab account doing the same , and YAE including a dedicated news piece on the video in its May 2021 newsletter . CALIPER also included promotion for the video in their July 2021 newsletter .		

CALIPER Role Model interview with Prof. Ivana Podnar Žarko

YAE is part of the [CALIPER project](#), whose goal is to make research organizations more gender equal by increasing the number of female researchers in STEM, improving their career prospects and integrating a gender dimension in research. Within this project YAE is responsible for the development of promotional videos to raise awareness and generate debate about gender inequality issues in STEM fields. The interviewees are role models, whose remarkable achievements can encourage other women, especially young girls, to become engaged with research and innovation. We would like to invite you to watch an interview with Professor Ivana Podnar Žarko from the University of Zagreb. You can find the full video [here](#).

Figure 7. YAE newsletter May 2021

Figure 8. CALIPER tweet

UZG-FER also wrote a [news piece](#) on the interview and published it on their website (below). They published their role model video on Girl's in ICT Day, (April 27th, 2021) and did a Facebook promotion campaign alongside.

Figure 9. UZG-FER Facebook post

Figure 10. UZG-FER news item

Figure 11. UZG-FER tweet

UZG-FER were also able to ask World Bank Croatia to post on Facebook to promote the interview, with their post receiving 230 views.

Figure 12. World Bank Croatia Facebook post

As part of the role model project, UZG-FER set up a website for future female students and collated all the videos with other female role models who started their professional careers at FER. They created a podcast ('ŽensCast') as part of the CALIPER project and the implementation of the FER Gender Equality plan, which promoted the main role model video as well as the CALIPER project.

FER - Zavod za primijenjenu matematiku
April 22, 2021 · 🌐

💡 Međunarodni dan djevojaka u ICT-u 💡

Fakultet elektrotehnike i računarstva Sveučilišta u Zagrebu uključio se u projekt Caliper – povezivanje istraživanja i inovacija za ravnopravnost spolova koji financira se u okviru Obzora 2020.

Povodom Međunarodnog dana djevojaka u ICT-u promoviraju se ženski uzori iz znanosti i istraživanja - osobe čija izvanredna osobnost, postignuća i pozitivna priča mogu potaknuti druge (posebno žene i mlade djevojke) da se bave istraživanjem i inovacijama.

Prof. dr. sc. Ivana Podnar Žarko je redovita profesorica na FER - Zavod za telekomunikacije. Njeni znanstveni interesi pripadaju području ICT-ja i trenutno vodi FER-ov Laboratorij za internet stvari. Nadamo se da će video intervju u kojem je svojim riječima opisala svoj školski i istraživački put, inspirirati mnoge.

Linkovi:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=M6Ayaib6HLLU>
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yGU5OLwzXpE&t=5s>
[Caliper EU \(caliper-project.eu, https://caliper-project.eu/role-models/\)](https://caliper-project.eu)
 Ivana Podnar Žarko (www.fer.unizg.hr/en/ivana.podnar_zarko)

See Translation

Figure 13. UZG-FER Gender Equality plan promotion

Women's Cast

ŽensCast is a podcast through which we want to introduce future students to women who started their professional career at FER. Through their stories and experiences, we want to invite and encourage future female students to choose to study at FER. Find more about the studies at [the link](#).

ŽensCast was created in collaboration with employees of the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing, and members of the [Women in Engineering Interest group of the Croatian IEEE section](#). The host of the podcast and the president of WIE IEEE Croatia is [Assoc. Prof. Ph.D. Pina Milišić](#). ŽensCast was created as part of the [Caliper](#) project and the implementation of [the FER Gender Equality Plan](#).

[#jednakeprilike@fer](https://twitter.com/jednakeprilike@fer)

Figure 14. UZG-FER podcast 'ŽensCast'

Further video promotion was made via the YAE December 2021 [Newsletter](#), as well as a dedicated post on the YAE [website](#) signposting viewers to the CALIPER role model videos webpage. CALIPER also included promotion for the video in their [July 2021 newsletter](#).

Professor Ivana Podnar Žarko

Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing, University of Zagreb, Croatia

"I always enjoy working on projects that are practical in nature."

[WATCH THE INTERVIEW](#)

Figure 15. CALIPER website post

The video has received 325 views since its launch in April 2022.

Link to the
YouTube
video

[Link to video on YouTube](#)

2.5 Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia, SRNSFG (Georgia)

Responsible partner	SRNSFG	Contributing partner(s)	VIL
Role model interviewee	Professor Ia Pipia		
Background information	<p>Professor Ia Pipia is a role model with STEM Women Asia, an online directory of women in Asia and Oceania working in STEM subjects. This project aims to promote gender equity in STEM by showcasing the breadth of scientific talent in the region, enabling a diverse range of women to be offered exciting opportunities to progress their careers and personal capabilities. Professor Ia Pipia's profile was featured in The Association of Academies and Societies of Sciences in Asia (AASSA) 'Profiles of Women Scientists in Asia' where she contributed her inspirational story and spoke on gender equality, making her an ideal candidate for the CALIPER role model interview.</p>		
Production process	<p>The third and last video completed by YAE was an interview with role model Professor Ia Pipia, Molecular geneticist at Agricultural University of Georgia. The video was filmed in-person by a third part videographer, as COVID-19 restrictions had started to lift at this point.</p>		
Dissemination of the interview	<p>The video was posted on CALIPER's role model webpage. An initial promotional tweet was sent out by CALIPER and SRNSFG, with the YAE including a link to the videos in their December 2021 Newsletter, as well as a dedicated post on the YAE website signposting viewers to the CALIPER role model videos webpage. SRNSFG also promoted the video on their website.</p> <p>As part of CALIPER's 2023 International Women's Day campaign, they reshared the video and promoted it via LinkedIn (below). The video was launched in June 2021, and as of March 2023 has 361 views.</p> <div data-bbox="574 1422 1225 1989" style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 10px; margin: 10px auto; width: fit-content;"> <p>Professor Ia Pipia</p> <p>Agricultural University of Georgia, Tbilisi, Georgia</p> <p><i>"Curiosity has always pushed me towards the process of acquiring knowledge."</i></p> <p>WATCH THE INTERVIEW</p> </div>		

Figure 16. CALIPER website

Figure 17. SRNSFG re-tweet

Figure 18. CALIPER tweet

Link to the YouTube video

[Link to video on YouTube](#)

2.6 National Technical University of Athens, NTUA (Greece)

Responsible partner	NTUA	Contributing partner(s)	VIL
Role model interviewee	Professor Asimina Kiourti		
Background information	Professor Asimina Kiourti, chosen as she was in the earlier stages of her research career and would therefore balance well with the previous role model interviewees who are more established in their careers. She was also an example of a female academic building a successful career in a leading US university.		
Production process	This was the first video that Cardiff University actioned, following their participation in the CALIPER project since 1 st October 2021. CU and NTUA worked closely in creating a script for the interview. As well as a full-length video, shortened videos were created for promotional purposes.		
Dissemination of the interview	Initially, promotion was launched in June 2022 via CALIPER's website, Twitter and LinkedIn accounts, with individual follow up from CU's Twitter/Facebook and NTUA. The CU website post launched shortly after the video was made available, with the written interview and a link to both the video and a PDF editorial of the interview (a Greek version was also sent to NTUA). NTUA also shared a dedicated news item and Professor Kiourti kindly shared the interview within her own network, as did her institution Ohio State University (below and here). A series of tweets were sent out from CU's twitter account sharing the short social media clips of the interview.		

Assistant Professor Asimina Kiourti

Electrical and Computer Engineering, Ohio State University, USA

"It's important to know that no woman is alone. All of us have been there in one way or another."

[WATCH THE INTERVIEW](#)

Figure 19. CALIPER website

	National Technical University of Athens School of Electrical and Computer Engineering	Education Undergraduate Postgraduate Doctoral ERASMUS	Research Impact Laboratories ICCS Libraries	People Academic Laboratory Research Administrative	School History Organization Access Contact
	100 years of education and research on the cutting edge of technology				
	1917-2017				
	CALIPER @Women in research and innovation: Associate Professor Asimina Kiourti				

Within the framework of "CALIPER project – Gender Equality in STEM research", the project partners implement a series of interviews with women working in research and innovation.

Mrs **Asimina Kiourti** has been selected for the interview of the **School of Electrical and Computer Engineering** of the **NTUA**, as she has received her doctorate degree in **ECE-NTUA** and is currently an Associate Professor in the School of Electrical and Computing Engineering at the Ohio State University.

The discussion with **Associate Prof. Asimina Kiourti** included topics such as the reasons that motivated her to choose her career in STEM, her experiences, obstacles that she faced on the way, as well as the advice she would give to young female students eager to follow a career in STEM.

The entire interview is available here:

Figure 20. NTUA new item

Figure 21. Ohio State University tweet

Figure 22. CU Academia Europaea Facebook post

Figure 23. CU Editorial

This interview was promoted to an extensive audience via newsletters; first via the Academia Europaea Cardiff Knowledge Hub July 2022 [newsletter](#) (image below) and also SAPEA’s [June 2022 Newsletter](#), which is sent to over 1k recipients in the science for policy area. It was also promoted to CALIPER’s audience via a [dedicated newsletter](#).

PROJECTS: CALIPER

AE Cardiff Hub hosts CALIPER consortium meeting

AE Cardiff was delighted to host CALIPER's 6th Project Management Team meeting on 22nd and 23rd June, at Woburn House in London.

33 consortium partners from across Europe were in attendance, either in person or online. Over the course of the two-day meeting, project partners had the opportunity to update colleagues on their progress within the [CALIPER project](#) and to share ideas and discuss challenges.

[Read about the meeting.](#)

Promoting gender equality in STEM

Watch our [series of CALIPER role model interviews](#), featuring women with remarkable personalities, achievements, and positive stories, with the aim of encouraging other women, especially young girls, to become engaged with research and innovation.

Our upcoming video will feature Dr. Adriana Albini, the Scientific Director of Fondazione MultiMedica Onlus, Milan.

Figure 24. Academia Europaea Cardiff Knowledge Hub July 2022 newsletter

Our role model Assist. Prof. Asimina Kiourti shares her experience as a woman in STEM

"It's important to know that no woman is alone. All of us have been there in one way or another"

For the fourth CALIPER role model video, our Greek partners from the School of Electrical and Computing Engineering from NTUA invited Assistant Professor Asimina Kiourti, a doctoral graduate of the School, who is currently holding a position at the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering at the Ohio State University.

As an assistant professor at the university, she has established a laboratory, that works on Wearable and Implantable Technologies (WIT). The laboratory carries out interdisciplinary work at the intersection of (bio-)electromagnetics, sensors, materials, and medicine, by developing wearables and implants.

During the interview she gave to our colleague Dr Maria Flouri, Asimina talked about the factors that led her to pursue a career in the STEM field. She expressed her vision for the future of women in R&I and STEM and shared with us the piece of advice she found helpful as a female student.

Watch the full interview and discover more about her and her work below!

Figure 25. CALIPER May newsletter

Since the initial launch, further promotion was made as part of CALIPER's 2023 International Women's Day campaign on [LinkedIn](#) and [Twitter](#) (below) and [again](#) when news of Professor Kiourti's promotion to Assistant Professor was made public.

Figure 26. CALIPER's 2023 IWD promotional post

As of April 2023, the video has 302 views on YouTube, with the shorted promotional videos appearing on people's Twitter feeds over 3k times (example analytics from 2 minute 'highlight reel' video below).

Figure 27. Twitter analytics

Link to the YouTube video

Το έργο έχει χρηματοδοτηθεί από το Πρόγραμμα Έρευνας και Καινοτομίας της Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης "Ορίζοντας 2020", στο πλαίσιο της Συμφωνίας Επιχορήγησης Αρ. 8733134

[Link to video on YouTube](#)

2.7 Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development & Innovation Funding in Romania, UEFISCDI (Romania)

Responsible partner	UEFISCDI	Contributing partner(s)	VIL
Role model interviewee	Dr Virginia Petre (née Vasile)		
Background information	The interviewee was Dr Virginia Petre (née Vasile), who has been a strong voice in the Research & Development community for gender equality and speaks passionately on the subject. We were particularly interested in interviewing her not just for her enthusiasm in the relevant area, but her engaging manner and professionalism on camera, which was evidenced clearly at the ‘My Thesis in 180 Seconds’ international competition at which she was a finalist.		
Production process	<p>The interview was filmed remotely using a third-party videographer. CU drafted interview questions that focused on Dr Petre’s interest and experiences in gender equality, and her experiences as a young researcher.</p> <p>CU worked closely with UEFISCDI in creating a script for the interview. Interviewer Oana Ionescu, Project Expert at UEFISCDI, spoke at length with Dr Petre. As well as a full-length video, several shortened videos were created for promotional purposes.</p>		
Dissemination of the interview	<p>The post was initially shared on social media via several routes; Facebook, CALIPER’s Twitter, and CU’s Twitter (with a two minute teaser video) and CALIPER’s LinkedIn page. Follow up tweets were sent from CU with the short social media teaser videos, which when combined with views on the CALIPER tweets, resulted in views of nearly 900 in total. UEFISCDI also tweeted in Romanian and shared on their Facebook account (below, totaling nearly 500 views), which has a following of 7k. Dr Petre shared with her email network and via LinkedIn, and a press release was sent out via EU Agenda. In addition the interview was spot lit in CU’s Winter newsletter, sent to all members of Academia Europaea, and to CALIPER’s network via a dedicated newsletter.</p> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 10px;"> <h3>Videos</h3> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Virginia Petre, cercetător în cadrul Universității Politehnica din București ...</p> <p>9 weeks ago · 268 views</p> </div> </div> </div>		

Figure 28. UEFISCDI Facebook posts

Figure 29. CALIPER tweet

Figure 30. EU Agenda press release

Figure 31. Twitter analytics

Figure 32. CU Academia Europaea Knowledge Hub's newsletter

Figure 33. CALIPER newsletter

The written interview was also launched on the CU Academia Europaea [website](#) where it remains popular, topping our 'most viewed' items, with over 100 visits in January 2023 alone and over 5 minute per article read (highlighted below). We have also created a written [PDF editorial](#) in English and Romanian, available for download on the website.

Most popular webpages

Page	Unique Pag...	Avg. Time on Page	Entrances	Bounce Rate	% Exit
1. /2022/08/21/putting-people-first-how-do-we-care-for-each-other-build-re...	376	00:04:31	352	89.77%	86.68%
2. /	272	00:01:29	243	55.97%	39.18%
3. /2023/01/05/i-want-young-girls-to-know-that-it-is-perfectly-normal-to-w...	110	00:05:17	92	86.96%	78.4%
4. /2022/08/21/physiology-pathophysiology-2023-symposium/	44	00:04:15	32	90.63%	70.59%

Figure 34. AE website analytics

Further promotion was made as part of CALIPER's 2023 International Women's Day campaign on [LinkedIn](#) and [Twitter](#).

Figure 35. CALIPER IWD tweet

Figure 36. CALIPER UWD LinkedIn post

Link to the YouTube video

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 873134

[Link to video on YouTube](#)

2.8 Research in Biomedicine, IRB (Spain)

Responsible partner	IRB	Contributing partner(s)	VIL
Role model interviewee	Professor Ángela Neito		
Background information	For the interview with Spanish partner IRB we interviewed Ángela Neito, an eminent biochemist whose achievements have been recognized by many prestigious international and national awards, such as the European International L’Oreal UNESCO 2019 Women in Science award .		
Production process	<p>The interview was conducted by María Macías, IRB Research Professor, who worked with CU (and with input from Professor Neito) in drafting a series of questions based on Professor Neito’s background and achievements.</p> <p>The interview was filmed remotely via a third party videographer, who also created a series of shortened videos for promotional purposes as well as a full-length video.</p>		
Dissemination of the interview	<p>On 28th Feb 2023 the initial CALIPER launch tweet had excellent engagement with 1770 views, and further tweets were sent out from the CALIPER account over the next few days to further promote the view. CU also launched a twitter campaign which has received good engagement via 1k+ tweet impressions (below).</p> <div data-bbox="555 1099 1230 1680" data-label="Image"> </div> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 37. CU AE’s Tweet</i></p>		

Figure 38. CALIPER tweet

IRB Barcelona also worked to promote the interview in the local language, [tweeting](#) and posting on [Instagram](#) and [Facebook](#). In addition, IRB posted the English video on [LinkedIn](#) to its 21.5k followers, which had excellent engagement.

Figure 39. IRB Instagram post

Figure 40. IRB tweet

Figure 41 - IRB LinkedIn post

The written interview and video were posted on the CU Academia Europaea Cardiff Knowledge hub [website](#) alongside an [editorial PDF](#) of the interview.

"We have to provide role models and show young women that not only can it be done, it can be done well." An interview with Ángela Nieto

As part of the CALIPER project, we are conducting a series of interviews with inspirational women who work in STEM research and innovation. We explore what motivated them to choose their career, their experiences and the barriers that they faced.

About Ángela Nieto

Professor Ángela Nieto achieved her PhD in biochemistry and molecular biology from the

Figure 42. CU AE's website news item

Professor Ángela Nieto

Institute of Neurosciences in Alicante, Spain

"I tell young girls that if they like science, please do it, because we need them."

[WATCH THE INTERVIEW](#)

Figure 43. CALIPER website post

As part of CALIPER's 2023 International Women's Day campaign, the video was reshared on [LinkedIn](#) and [Twitter](#). Both the Spanish and English videos are posted on YouTube and have a collective viewing of 76.

Figure 44. CALIPER IWD LinkedIn post

Figure 45. CALIPER IWD tweet

Link to the YouTube video

Professor Ángela Neito
Institute of Neurosciences
Alicante, Spain

Interview Dr María Macías
Institute For Research in Biomedicine
Barcelona, Spain

CALIPER
Gender Equality in STEM Research

Role Model Interview

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 873134.

[Link to video on YouTube](#)

2.9 Salento University, UNILE (Italy)

Responsible partner	UNILE	Contributing partner(s)	VIL
Role model interviewee	Professor Adriana Albini		
Background information	<p>UNILE chose Professor Adriana Albini for their role model interview, a pathologist and cancer researcher with both esteemed academic and industry credentials. She works simultaneously across both areas, acting both as Professor of General Pathology at Milano Bicocca University and the Scientific Director of the Fondazione MultiMedica Onlus in Milan. Not only is she among the most cited Italian women scientists, she featured as one of ‘the BBC’s 100 Women of 2020’ highlighting those who were “leading change and making a difference during turbulent times” making her an excellent role model to act as an inspiration to others.</p>		
Production process	<p>CU drafted a series of interview questions focused on Professor Albini’s background in cancer research, her experience in both research and industry focused roles, and her public accolades. The interview was conducted by Simona Martano, PhD student in Physics and Nanoscience at Salento University, who spoke at length with Professor Albini. A third-party videographer filmed the video remotely, and created a full length interview from the footage as well as several short promotional videos.</p>		
Dissemination of the interview	<p>CALIPER published the interview on the main CALIPER role model webpage. The interview was featured on the CU Cardiff Knowledge Hub main page as a news item and transcribed as a written interview.</p> <div data-bbox="478 1232 1308 1904" style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 10px; margin: 10px 0;"> <p>Dr Adriana Albini University of Milano-Bicocca</p> <p><i>“I want young women to not stop fighting.”</i></p> <p>WATCH THE INTERVIEW</p> </div> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>Figure 46. CALIPER website post</i></p>		

Figure 47. CU Academia Europaea website news item

Figure 48. CU Academia Europaea website post

CU Academia Europaea's [Spring Newsletter](#) was sent to over 4k AE members, and included a spotlight on the CALIPER videos, linking to the main site. The link to the AE Cardiff Knowledge Hub website #rolemodel hashtag drove 45 clicks though to the the articles on the interviews.

Figure 49. CU Academia Europaea's Spring Newsletter

CALIPER's initial launch [tweet](#) included the two-minute [promotional](#) video, which had nearly 285 views. Milano Bicocca University's [twitter](#) promoted the video of CU Academia Europaea Cardiff Knowledge Hub's tweet (299 views) and the CU Academia Europaea launch [tweet](#) had 300 views. Combined, the two-minute video was actively watched nearly 900 times. Academia Europaea Cardiff Knowledge Hub followed up with a [tweet campaign](#) to further promote the interview.

Figure 50. CU Academia Europaea tweet

Figure 51. CALIPER tweet

UNILE also shared on social media via [Twitter](#), [Instagram](#) and [Facebook](#) with over 400 views combined.

Figure 52. UNILE Instagram post

Figure 53. UNILE re-tweet

Figure 54. UNILE tweet

Figure 55. UNILE Facebook post

As of April 2023, the video has 66 views on YouTube since its launch on 8th March.

Link to the
YouTube
video

[Link to video on YouTube](#)

2.10 Yasar University YU (Turkey)

Responsible partner	YU	Contributing partner(s)	VIL
Role model interviewee	Prof. Dr Kevser Özgen Özer		
Background information	<p>Prof. Dr Kevser Özgen Özer is a professor at Ege University. Professor Özer was a particularly inspiring choice to interview, given her fascinating background as an academic researcher who successfully transferred the results of her own scientific research to market. Professor Özer led an all-female team (below) that patented and brought to market Dermalix, a wound healing skincare product.</p> <p>The photograph shows three women, likely members of Professor Özer's team, standing outdoors in front of a statue. They are all wearing white lab coats and are smiling while taking a selfie with a smartphone. The woman on the left is holding the phone up to take the picture.</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 56. Professor Özer and her team</i></p>		
Production process	<p>In drafting the interview, CU completed background research on Professor Özer to create a series of questions, focusing on how Prof. Özer navigated combining entrepreneurship with her academic role, the challenges around this, and how women can increase their role in inventing and developing successful products.</p> <p>YU were able to complete filming on site, due to their professional media suite within the university and completed editing of the full length video, as well as a shorter version for promotional purposes.</p>		
Dissemination of the interview	<p>The video launched in early April 2023. As well as the YouTube video upload, the interview was posted to the CALIPER website. The written interview and video link were posted on the CU Academia Europaea Cardiff Knowledge Hub's website (and shared on the main page as a headline news item).</p>		

Prof. Dr. Özgen Özer

Ege University

"Many young people can go great miles when they are given the opportunity and path. I advise them to never lose their motivation!"

[WATCH THE INTERVIEW](#)

Figure 57. CALIPER website post

Figure 58. CU Academia Europaea website homepage

CALIPER promoted the video via their [Facebook](#), [Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#) accounts, where it received excellent engagement. CU also [tweeted](#) a link to the video, including the short promotional video created by YU which has received 213 views.

Figure 59. CALIPER LinkedIn post

Figure 60. CALIPER tweet

Figure 61. CU Academia Europaea tweet

CU also promoted the video in their Academia Europaea [Spring newsletter](#), sent to the network of over 4k members of Academia Europaea. The newsletter had good engagement, with a 45% open and read rate.

In the three weeks since the video went live on YouTube, it has received 63 views (as of April 2023).

Link to the
YouTube
video

[Link to video on YouTube](#)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

2.11 Université libre de Bruxelles, ULB (Belgium)

Responsible partner	ULB	Contributing partner(s)	VIL
Role model interviewee	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Karine Van Doninck, Professor, Unité de recherche Molecular Biology & Evolution (MBE) 2. Alessia Cuccurullo, Assistant Professor, ULB 3. Sarah Wauthy, PhD student, ULB 4. Nora Laaroussi, MSc Student and Vice-President of WomInTech, ULB 		
Background information	<p>The ULB role model video took a different approach, choosing to cater the video to a very specific target audience, which accordingly changed the approach to the video planning. They wanted a short, engaging video that would be shown to young girls (ages 5-15) interested in STEM, in order to inspire them. The short length of the video (5 minutes) was chosen in order to keep the viewers engaged, as it was deemed a longer question and answer video would not suit the target audience.</p>		
Production process	<p>CU worked closely with ULB on drafting interview questions that would generate interesting answers to keep young girls interested- the aim was for short, engaging answers rather than the more in-depth answers generated by previous interviews. A draft outline was created by ULB (below) which summarised the key points of the video and ensured the objectives were clearly defined.</p> <div data-bbox="477 1070 1324 1955" style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 10px;"> <p>CONCEPT NOTE: CALIPER-ULB ROLE MODEL INITIATIVE</p> <p>SPOTLIGHT ON – INSPIRING WOMEN IN STEM</p> <p>Purpose: Create an engaging and interactive video that features a diversity of women across career stages and inspires a next generation of female scientists. A video that breaks both gender and science stereotypes and can be widely disseminated.</p> <p>Target audience The next generation of female scientists: young women and girls aged 15-23 - who are beginning to contemplate their first study choice or continued studies.</p> <p>How: ● Feature 4 diverse women: across both STEM faculties and career levels → Role models: 2 from EPB 2 from Science Faculty → Levels: Student PhD Early career professor Senior professor</p> <p>What: ● We seek to create content that can inspire any young women contemplating their future study choices. We travel into the scientific life of our role models with a look behind the scenes of the work they do and spotlight what inspires them in their professional career path and personal purpose. [Birds eye view to break down complexity] → Practically - same set of questions are asked to all 4 role models [best footage to be selected]</p> <p>Duration & Set up: ● Video length: approx. 5min [based on attention span of the younger target group] → Snippets will be extracted from the footage for shorter promotional activities/social media Language: French Sub: English/French (two versions) ● Interview style in a visually appealing location connected to role models scientific context → will be combined with B roll footage - showing role models in their hands-on real work environments e.g lecturing; conducting experiments in a lab; field visit etc.]</p> </div>		

Figure 62. proposal outline 1

Sneak Peek - Video Structure & Content

- 1. Introduction of the role model**
 - Name/position/faculty/ how long they are working there/ topic/disciplinary focus
→ will be inserted as a text caption in the video
- 2. Role model journey - career & science inspiration**
A set of questions asked to all 4 role models helping us understand their journey
 - Tell us why you chose to become a scientist (what sparked your interest) [Inspiration]
 - What excites you most now about working in science? [STEM Innovation]
 - What's been the highlight of your career so far? [Career journey]
 - Who were the people who had the greatest impact on your work and career?
 - What's your one message/advice to the next generation of young women scientists? [Advice to the next generation]

[Any suggestions on questions are welcome!]
- 3. Wrap-up: Diversity & Possibilities in Science**
 - For inclusivity we seek to feature 4-5 further women across ages and levels - to broadly *highlight gender and diversity* in both faculties.
 - These women (and the role models) will answer a **single question in one word**:
"In ONE word what does science mean to you"
 → we look for **'unconventional/creative' descriptions** of what science can be - beyond mainstream notions that may have been taught/suggested to us
 e.g. *Discovery | Problem solving | Sustainable | Explore | Collaborate ...*
 - The ONE-word answers create a **final compilation scene of approx. 30 seconds**
 - We may end the vid with a final wide shot - simply showing the faces of all women we featured [TBC]

PRACTICAL PARTS
- Consortium partner Cardiff University (CU) coordinates video production

Figure 63. Proposal outline 2

In addition to being shown to young girls in STEM, the intention is to use the video for a wide spectrum of activities:

- Internally diffuse into ULB's gender steering committee, and disseminate into the wider ULB audience as well as distribute externally
- Publish to the dedicated gender equality webpages in each of the ULB STEM faculties. It will also be shared with the services in each STEM faculty responsible for outreach
- Inclusion of the video in the 'onboarding' process for new STEM students
- Used as a tool in future recruitment of new students
- Discussions are currently in phase with Centre for Research in Educational Sciences, Faculty of Psychological Sciences and Education, ULB to work on the formation of secondary teachers, in alignment with, "Pact for Teaching Excellence: Mathematics, Science, Geography - manual, technical, technological and digital training" under the Ministry of the Wallonia-Brussels Federation. The video would be published on a e-learning site and part of the training for this scheme.

A key aim of the video was to provide as much diversity as possible within the role models chosen; they ranged from early career starter (MSc Student) to later career points (Professor) covering a range of STEM subjects and different ethnicities and nationalities.

A specialist videographer with extensive University project experience was chosen to film and edit the interviews. As a bonus, the videographer had two young daughters who were in the age range we were looking to target, which not only have him a personal passion and interest in the project but access to the exact demographic to

	<p>obtain relevant feedback during the editing process. The videographer met with all role models prior to filming, in order to obtain b-roll footage of them in their working environment to include in the video and to give them ample opportunity to ask questions and get used to being on camera. Several locations around ULB campus were also scouted to ensure the best possible backdrop for the interviews themselves.</p> <p>Once a draft version was completed, both ULB, CU and VIL were able to feedback comments to integrate into the final video version.</p>
<p>Dissemination of the interview</p>	<p>The final version was uploaded to CALIPER's YouTube on April 21st, 2023, while the interview was posted in the dedicated section in CALIPER website. Further video promotion is planned throughout April and May, with ULB planning to disseminate the video internally and via institutional networks.</p> <p>In particular, the ULB video will be disseminated through activities that have been carried out for all the above-mentioned videos, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • News item on CU Academia Europaea website • Promotion via CALIPER's social media accounts (Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn) and subsequent social media promotion via CU and ULB's accounts/pages. • Dedicated feature in upcoming CALIPER newsletter issue(s) • Promotion of the video during online campaigns for International Days • Post on ULB's institutional website • Dissemination in local media via ULB's institutional network • Presentation of the video in the context of institutional events (i.e., university's open days and public info sessions, awareness activities jointly with Secondary Education institutions)
<p>Link to the YouTube video</p>	<p><i>Figure 64: Link to YouTube video</i></p>

2.12 Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, STU BA (Slovakia)

Responsible partner	STU BA	Contributing partner(s)	VIL
Role model interviewee	Assoc. Professor Ivona Čerňičková		
Background information	<p>The interviewee was Assoc. Professor Ivona Čerňičková from Institute of Materials Science of the Faculty of Materials Science and Technology in Trnava, Slovak University of Technology. Professor Čerňičková has extensively published the results of her scientific research work in over 30 publications registered in WOS and Scopus. She is cited, and she regularly participates in international scientific conferences.</p>		
Production process	<p>STU BA were able to complete filming on site, including a face-to-face interview and ample b-roll footage of Professor Čerňičková in her working environment, and also completed editing of the video.</p> <div data-bbox="448 974 1356 1442" data-label="Image"> </div> <p><i>Figure 65. b-roll footage of Professor Čerňičková</i></p>		
Dissemination of the interview	<p>The final version was uploaded to CALIPER's YouTube on April 28th, 2023, and the video is also available at the dedicated section in CALIPER website. CU and VIL will undertake the dissemination of the video based on a tailored plan throughout May and June while with STU BA is going to further promote it internally and via institutional networks.</p> <p>Following the approach that has been successfully implemented for all the previous interviews, the STU BA video dissemination will consist of the actions below:</p>		

- News item on CU Academia Europaea website
- Promotion via CALIPER's social media accounts (Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn) and subsequent social media promotion via CU and STU BA's accounts/pages.
- Dedicated feature in upcoming CALIPER newsletter issue(s)
- Promotion of the video during online campaigns for International Days
- Post on STU BA's institutional website
- Dissemination in local media via STU BA's institutional network
- Presentation of the video in the context of institutional events (i.e., university's open days and public info sessions, awareness activities jointly with Secondary Education institutions)

Link to the
YouTube video

Figure 66 Link to YouTube video

3 Key Performance Indicators

3.1 KPI targets

The KPIs for Deliverable 6.7 have been met and surpassed, as evidenced below (as of April 2023). Video views have been collected from YouTube statistics on each video and collated. The promotional videos aim was to reach at least 600 researchers and academics. Given the multiple newsletter and websites where role model videos have been featured, and the reach of CALIPER and CU social media and subscriber networks, we have reached more than 600 researchers and academics.

In addition, the short promotional videos have been viewed on Twitter collectively over 5,400 times. AE Cardiff Hub's 1k twitter following is a mix of academics, researchers, and industry, making it an ideal target audience for dissemination of the role model videos.

At this point it is essential to note that the dissemination of the role model videos is a continuous effort. That is, the initial interviews will still be promoted, while the most recent ones (namely ULB and STU BA videos) are going to be disseminated following a strategy that has already brought good results for all the previous cases. In this sense, further metrics and reporting of these videos will be considered and it will be provided in the final dissemination activities reporting (D6.4), to provide a long-term overview of the impact and the outcomes of this task.

KPIs:

Description	Measurement type	Target	Achieved
At least 600 views of videos by researchers and academics	Number of views	600	1709

Individual breakdown of views:

Partner	Video Publication Date	Number of views
YAE (Pilot Video)	Dec 21, 2020	255
UZG-FER	Apr 22, 2021	325
SRNSFG	Jun 10, 2021	361
NTUA	May 23, 2022	302
UEFISCDI	Jan 5, 2023	231
IRB	Feb 20, 2023	76
UNILE	Mar 8, 2023	66
YU	April 1, 2023	63
ULB	April 23, 2023	20
STU BA	May 2023, TBC	10
	TOTAL:	1709

3.2 Deliverables and milestones

Del. No	Deliverable name	WP	Lead participant	Dissemination level	Delivery date
6.7	Role models report	6	CU	PU	M40

MS. No	Milestone Title	WP	Lead participant	Due date	Means of verification
6.2	Role model videos	6	CU	M40	Videos completed and launched

4 Conclusion

The CALIPER role model videos have been an effective tool in promoting gender equality in STEM fields. Filming the interview in the native language of the role models has had several benefits, including recognition of the local community, and allowing partners to reach a wider audience with the video. Featuring role models speaking in their native language allows viewers to connect with the community on a more personal level; the aim was to create a sense of familiarity and authenticity, making it easier for women to relate to the role models and feel inspired by their stories. Additionally, by featuring role models who are speaking in their own language, the videos can serve as a source of motivation for viewers, particularly women from that country who may feel underrepresented in STEM fields. Filming in the local language can also help to reach a wider audience; by using multiple languages, the videos can be shared and viewed by a diverse range of people, increasing their overall impact.

Promoting the CALIPER role model videos on social media has been an important aspect of the project, as it allows for widespread distribution and access to viewers from diverse backgrounds. Social media platforms such as Twitter, Facebook, and LinkedIn are ideal channels to share content and reach a wide audience and we have extensively utilised these platforms in video promotion. One of the key benefits of promoting the videos on social media is the ability to reach viewers from different backgrounds and locations. By sharing the videos on social media platforms, CALIPER has been able to reach individuals who may not have had access to the videos through traditional media channels. Social media also allowed for the videos to be shared and viewed by individuals outside of the initial target audience, increasing their overall impact and visibility. The impact of the videos can be seen through the high engagement rates and tweet impressions, indicating that the videos have resonated with viewers and sparked awareness around gender equality.

In addition, social media platforms provide opportunities for engagement and discussion around the CALIPER role model videos. By promoting the videos on social media, viewers can easily share their thoughts, ask questions, and engage in conversation with others. Through continued promotion and engagement efforts, CALIPER can continue to make an impact and drive change in the STEM community. Furthermore, the sustainability of the videos means that they can continue to be used for years to come, making them an important asset for the CALIPER project in continuing to promote gender equality in STEM fields.

Later in 2023, CU plans an international webinar, which will reach across Europe and beyond, to promote the videos collectively.

